

Present Scenario of Phaeophyceae Utilization

Periyasamy Thangamathi, Veerapandiyan Thangapandian*, Kaliappan Nalini, Ponnirul Ponmanickam and Thangavel Sivakumar

Department of Microbiology, Ayya Nadar Janaki Ammal College, Sivakasi, Tamilnadu, India.

*Corresponding author: Veerapandiyan Thangapandian, E-mail: mybacterium@gmail.com

Received: May 13, 2015, Accepted: June 9, 2015, Published: June 9, 2015.

ABSTRACT

Agar is an algal polysaccharide widely used in biological research, food and Pharmaceutical industries as gelling agents, thickeners, stabilizers, emulsifiers etc. Overexploitation of Agar will lead to the loss of Agar yielding algal population particularly *Gracilaria* and *Gelidium* sp. from the environment which are the important component of marine biodiversity. The commercial exploitation of seaweeds from the natural seaweed beds of Tamil Nadu is approximately 6000 tonnes (dry weight) per year. Agarose is one of the expensive algal materials. Reusing of Agar in biological research would be helpful to conserve the biodiversity. To reduce the over exploitation of algal resources, there will be recycling process is required. Using reclaimed Agar will reduce the purchasing cost of Agarose as well as concern with biodiversity conservation. This review article is focused on the present scenario of Agarophytes, production, overexploitation, recycling of Agar and conservation strategies.

Keyword: Microbiology, Phaeophyceae, *Ethnobotany*, biological research.

INTRODUCTION

Agar or agar-agar is a gelatinous substance, obtained from algae and discovered in the late 1650s or early 1660s by Minoya Tarozaemon in Japan, where it is called as 'kanten'. Agar is derived from the polysaccharide Agarose, which forms the supporting structure in the cell wall of certain species of algae, and which is released on boiling. These algae are known as agarophytes and belong to the phylum Rhodophyta (red algae) [1]. The structure of Agar from *Gracilaria* consists of repeating units of D-galactose and 3,6-anhydro-L-galactose [2]. Agarose is a neutral polysaccharide with a linear structure of repeating units of the disaccharide Agarobiose, a dimer of D-galactose and 3,6-anhydro-L-galactose [3]. The structure of Agarose determined by Araki and Arai [4], consists of alternating copolymers of 1,4 linked 3,6-anhydro- α -L-galactose and 1,3 linked β -D-galactose. Sulphated polysaccharides (SPS) are the class of compounds containing hemi-ester sulphate groups in their sugar residues. These are commonly found in varying amounts in three major divisions of marine algal groups, viz. Rhodophyta, Phaeophyta and Chlorophyta. Sulphated polysaccharides found in Rhodophyta are galactans consisting entirely of galactose or modified galactose units. They are known commercially as Agar and Carrageenan [5].

Present scenario of Phaeophyceae Utilization

Agar extraction

Higuera *et al.* [6] evaluated the effects of alkali treatment and extraction time of native Agar and alkali treated Agar obtained from *Gracilaria vermiculophylla*. Ahmad *et al.* [7] investigated the Agar content and Agar gel strength from intact and squeezed thalli of *Gracilaria manilaensis*, collected from the earthen pond at Pantai Merdeka, Kedah, Malaysia.

Villanueva *et al.* [8] reported the utilization potential, in terms of Agar production, of the invasive alga, *Gracilaria vermiculophylla*, collected at Ria de Aveiro, Northwestern Portugal. The Agar yield ranged from 15% to 33%, with pre-extraction treatment with alkali generally increasing the yield. The gel quality (gel strength and apparent Young's modulus) was best (>600 g cm⁻² and $>1,000$ kPa, respectively) when alkali treatment with 6% NaOH for 3.5 hour was performed. Mateen *et al.* [9] tried with the eleven putative gelling agents as Agar substitutes. These included arrowroot (*Maranta arundinaceae*), coconut powder (*Cocos nucifera*), corn flour (*Zea mays var. amylacea*), gel rite (a water-soluble polysaccharide produced by *Sphingomonas elodea*), glue (*Cyanoacrylates*), katira gum (*Cochlospermum religiosum*), guar gum (*Cyamopsis tetragonolobus* L.), isubgol husk (*Plantago ovata*), pectin and rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) powder. They found that among these, guar gum was a promising alternate candidate for Agar.

Yousefi *et al.* [10] extracted the Agar from *Gracilaria corticata* by modifying various extraction variables such as soaking time, soaking temperature, seaweed to water ratio, extraction temperatures and extraction time and also alkali treatment method. Raiker *et al.* [11] collected *Gracilaria greville* from Japan, India and Malasiya. Growth rate experiments were conducted at different temperatures, salinities and light intensities. *Gracilaria vermiculophylla* was found to be a fast growing species with the growth rate of 22.32%. The growth rate of all species varied with salinities, but most of them attained their growth rate at normal seawater salinity 35%. Rao and Kladhran, [12] optimized the levels of alkali / acid and thermal manipulations during extraction of Agar to increase the yield and quality of Agar from red seaweed *Gracilaria edulis*

(Gmelin) Silva, Cirik *et al.* [13] cultivated the Agarophyte *Gracilaria verrucosa* (Hudson) under greenhouse conditions in the modified Johnson Medium over a 5-month period and concluded that it can be cultivated in greenhouse conditions. Prasad *et al.* [14] assessed the physiochemical and rheological properties of agar, extracted from 20 samples of *Gelidiella acerosa*, collected from Gujarat coast in various seasons. Their studies showed that *Gelidiella acerosa* of Okha can be used as a good source of Agar. Rheological data of the best Agar of the lot were also in good agreement with the other physiochemical data example, high gel strength Agar showed higher G' value and *vice versa*.

Lee *et al.* [15] reported the effect of sulfate starvation on the Agar characteristics of *Gracilaria* species by culturing two red algae *Gracilaria changii* and *Gracilaria salicornia* from Morib, Malaysia, and maintained in sulfate free artificial seawater for 5 days. Sulfate starvation introduced the variation in the content of 3,6-anhydrogalactose and total sulfate esters, but the changes did not have a pronounced effect on the physical properties of Agar. Sahu and Sahoo [16] observed the morphological, anatomical and Agar content difference between various species of *Gracilaria*. Agar from *Gracilaria verrucosa* (floating type or sterile type) showed highest yield with gel strength 260 gm/cm² and viscosity 10 mlipass.

Thangapandian *et al.* [17] reported that Agar is an algal polysaccharide widely used in biological research and as food additive. Overexploitation of Agar will lead to the loss of Agar yielding Algal population. Reuse of Agar in biological research may conserve the biosphere and the biodiversity. In this preliminary study they attempted to recover the used Agar by freeze-thawing method (Training manual on *Gracilaria* culture and sea weed processing in China, 2006). The recovered Agar samples are reused successfully in their laboratory for media preparations, which gives a hope for further research on utilization of used agar after recycling and step forward to conserve the agar.

Agarose Preparation

Jeon *et al.* [18] evaluated the quality of Agarose by analyzing the proximate chemical composition, sulfate content, gelling strength and DNA migration. The resolution power and the ligase activities gave clear picture about the suitability of their Agarose for practical purposes. Patent 1, [19] discloses a method for separating and preparing Agarose from Agar by using a polyethylene glycol precipitation method. Agarwal *et al.* [20] developed a convenient and energy efficient process for the preparation of Agarose from *Gracilaria* and *Gelidiella* sp. particularly from *Gracilaria dura* and *Gelidella acerosa* which are collected from Indian waters. The DNA gel electrophoresis studies showed the performance which is equal to that of gel obtained through more conventional process of Agarose preparation from the same seaweed.

Palacios *et al.* [21] reported the cost of Agarose for DNA gel electrophoresis can be significant in large scale projects. The International Potato Center (CIP) laboratory in Lima-Peni was reusing the Agarose to save money and environment. Due to the limited financial resources for research in Latin American laboratories, this practice satisfies a need manage expenses. Recycled Agarose can be used for RAPD analysis, or other applications in which no further manipulation of the DNA is necessary. Further they described an improved CIP method

where large amounts of Agarose are ultimately equilibrated in water and dried to get powder similar to the original Agarose. Souza *et al.* [22] assessed the hydrocolloids from seaweeds which are having interesting functional properties such as antioxidant potential and gelling ability. The rheological behavior of *Gracilaria birdiae* sulfated polysaccharide exhibits a gel-like behavior as in commercial Agar. The antioxidant properties of *Gracilaria birdiae* sulfated polysaccharide were evaluated by measuring DPPH free radical scavenging effect, showing that this polysaccharide has a moderate effect in inhibiting the formation of those radicals. Mussa *et al.* [23] estimated the concentration of the available phosphate, nitrate and sulfate in algal samples which were collected from different places at different depths.

CONCLUSION

From the above literatures it is concluded that recycling of used agar is a approachable method and it is very much helpful to conserve the algal biodiversity and prevent the overexploitation Algal population.

REFERENCES

1. N. Kaliaperumal, S. Kalimuthu, and J.R. Ramalingam, Present scenario of seaweed exploitation and industry in India, *Seaweed Res. Utiln.* 26(1&2): (2004) 47-53.
2. E.Y. Dawson, *Marine Botany: An Introduction.* Holt, Rinehart and Winston, New York, (1966) p. 371.
3. R. Jayasankar, S. Varghese, Growth and pigment constituents of the red alga *Gracilaria edulis* (Gmelin) Silva, grown at different depths, *Indian J. Fish.* 47(4): (2000) 365-369.
4. D.L.A. Higuera, Y. Elizabeth, R. Montesino, J.I.M. Alvarez, M.M. Ochoa, G.H. Carmona, Effect of alkali treatment time and extraction time on Agar from *Gracilaria vermiculophylla*, *J. Appl. Phyco.* 20: (2008) 515- 519.
5. M. Shanmugam, K.H. Mody, Heparinoid-active sulphated Polysaccharides from marine Algae as potential blood anticoagulant agents, *Current Science.* 79: (2000) 12.
6. D.L.A Higuera, Y. Elizabeth, R. Montesino, J.I.M. Alvarez, M.M. Ochoa, G.H. Carmona, Effect of alkali treatment time and extraction time on Agar from *Gracilaria vermiculophylla*, *J. Appl. Phyco.* 20: (2008) 515- 519.
7. R. Ahmad, M. Surif, Ramli, N. Yahya, A.R.M. Nor, L. Bekbayeva, A Preliminary study on the Agar content and Agar gel strength of *Gracilaria manilaensis* using different Agar extraction processes, *World Applied Sciences Journal.* 15(2): (2011) 184-188.
8. R.D. Villanueva, A.M.M. Sousa, M.P. Gonçalves, M. Nilsson, L. Hilliou, Production and properties of Agar from the invasive marine alga, *Gracilaria vermiculophylla* (Gracilariales, Rhodophyta), *J. Appl. Phycol.* 22: (2010) 211-220.
9. Mateen, S. Hussain, S.U. Rehman, B. Mahmood, M.A. Khan, A. Rashid, M. Sohail, M. Farooq, S.J.A. Shah, Suitability of various plant derived gelling agents as Agar substitute in microbiological growth media, *African Journal of Biotechnology.* 11(45): (2012) 10362-10367.
10. K. Yousefi, M.F. Yousef, R.E. Homan, M. Ali, A. Parviz, Optimization of extracting Agar of Persian Gulf's *Gracilaria corticata* algae, *Oceanography.* 1(4): (2011) 4-4.

11. S.V. Raikar, M. Lima, Y. Fujita, Effect of temperature, salinity and light intensity on the growth of *Gracilaria* sp. (Gracilariales, Rhodophyta) from Japan, Malasia and India, *Indian Journal of marine sciences.*, 30: (2001) 98-104.
12. A.C. Rao, P. Kaladharan, Improvement of yield and quality of Agar from *Gracilaria edulis* (Gmelin) Silva, *Seaweed Res. Utiln.* 25(182): (2003) 131-138.
13. S. Cirik, Z. Cetin¹, I. Ak, S. Cirik, T. Goksan, Greenhouse cultivation of *Gracilaria verrucosa* (Hudson) Papenfuss and determination of chemical composition, *Turkish Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences.* 10: (2010) 559-564.
14. K. Prasad, A.M. Goswami, R. Meena, B.K. Ramavat, P.K. Ghosh, A.K. Siddhanta, Superior quality Agar from red alga *Gelidiella acerosa* (Rhodophyta, Gelidiales) from Gujarat coast of India: An evaluation, *Indian Journal of Marine Sciences.* 35(3): (2006) 268-274.
15. W.K. Lee, P. Namasivayam, C.L. Ho, Effect of Sulfate starvation on Agar polysaccharides *Gracilaria* species (Gracilariaceae, Rhodophyta) from Morib and Malasiya, *J. Appl. Phycol.* Revied 11 Semtember (2013).
16. N. Sahu, D. Sahoo, Study of morphology and Agar contents in some important *Gracilaria* species of Indian Coasts, *American Journal of Plant Sciences.* 4: (2013) 52-59.
17. V. Thangapandian, M. Muthamilarasan, C. Manimuthu, M. Asma, K. Lingakumar, Recovery and recycling of Agar, *Advanced BioTech.* 9: (2009) Issue:05.
18. Y.J. Jeon, Y. Athukorala, J. Lee, Characterization of Agarose product from Agar using DMSO, *Faculty of Applied Marine Science.* 20(1): (2005) 61-67.
19. Patent 1, Patent CN101891835B - Method for separating and preparing Agarose from Agar by using Polyethylene Glycol precipitation method, September 20 (2013).
20. P.K. Agarwal, K. Eswaran, R.M. Gandhi, M.S. Ganesan, P.K. Ghosh, B. Jha, R. Meena, G.K. Mehta, A. Mishra, K. Prasad, B.K. Ramavat, A.K. Siddhanta, Process for the preparation of Agarose polymer from seaweed extractive, Patent EP2411418A1, (2012) filed Mar. 19, 2010, and issued Feb 1, 2012.
21. G. Palacios, C. Gimenez, E.D. Garcia, Recycling Agarose, *Plant Molecular Biology Reporter.* 18: (2000) 47-49.
22. B.W.S. Souza, M.A. Cerqueira, A.I. Bourbon, A.C. Pinheiro, J.T. Martins, J.A. Teixeira, M.A. Coimbra, A.A. Vicente, Chemical characterization and antioxidant activity of sulfated polysaccharide from the red seaweed *Gracilaria birdiae*, *Food Hydrocolloids.* 27: (2012) 287-292.
23. S.A.B. Mussa, H.S. Elferjani, F.A. Haroun, F.F. Abdelnabi, Determination of available nitrate, phosphate and sulfate in soil samples, *International Journal of Pharm Tech Research.* 1(3): (2009) 598-604.

Citation: Veerapandiyan Thangapandian *et al.*. (2015). Present Scenario of Phaeophyceae Utilization. *J. of Advanced Botany and Zoology*, V3I1. DOI: 10.15297/JABZ.V3I1.03.

Copyright: © 2015 Veerapandiyan Thangapandian. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.